

Marine litter in the Red Sea: Status and policy implications

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Abstract

The Red Sea's unique ecosystem is home to more than 1500 species. However, the presence of anthropogenic litter, whether from land-based or sea-based sources, may pose a potential risk to the Red Sea fauna and flora. This work analyzes marine litter in the Red Sea, utilizing the Drivers-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR) framework to group findings in a survey of peer-reviewed studies. The review is further augmented with a survey of the current response, covering regional and national instruments. Although research addressing marine litter in the Red Sea is not as rich as for other seas, studies suggest marine litter is abundant and that the influx of litter is driven by recreational activity, fishing, and shipping. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated the influx of marine litter to the Red Sea due to improper disposal of personal protective equipment (PPE). The response has intensified in recent years, with regional and national frameworks established and initiatives driven by Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs). We discuss whether the regional action plan addresses the specific concerns uncovered in marine litter studies while providing a comparison with plans of other regional seas.

28 **Keywords:** DPSIR, macro litter, micro litter, microplastics, plastic, policy instruments, solid waste

29 **1. Introduction**

30 Marine litter, defined as "any persistent, manufactured or processed solid material discarded, disposed
31 of or abandoned in the marine and coastal environment" (UNEP, 2016), is one of the most pressing
32 environmental problems the world is facing at the present. The history of marine litter research dates
33 back to the 1970s and is associated with the development of plastics (Ryan, 2015). The majority of
34 marine litter (61-87%) is composed of plastic, ranging in size and type (Bellou et al., 2021). Based on
35 a 2010 estimate, 192 coastal countries generated 275 million metric tons of plastic waste, of which 4.8
36 to 12.7 million metric tons entered the marine environment (Jambeck et al., 2015). The size of plastic
37 litter plays a critical role in the impact caused to marine biota and is accordingly divided into four
38 classes: micro (≤ 5 mm), meso (5-20 mm), macro (>20 mm), and mega (>100 mm) (Barboza et al.,
39 2019). Larger size plastics and fragments are known to cause entanglement, suffocation, and ingestion
40 incidents predominantly in birds, fish, and marine animals (Barboza et al., 2019; Gall and Thompson,
41 2015). On the other hand, smaller size plastics can be ingested by marine organisms causing adverse
42 effects (Botterell et al., 2022). Similarly, micro-sized plastics can act as sorbents and carriers of
43 contaminants and pathogens, leading to pollution and microbial invasion (Bowley et al., 2021; Tesfaldet
44 and Ndeh, 2022). Furthermore, the wide range of socio-economic impacts of marine litter, such as loss
45 of aesthetic value, tourism revenue, and recreational opportunity are well documented in the literature
46 (PNUMA et al., 2009).

47 There are numerous studies about the impact of anthropogenic marine litter on the marine fauna and
48 flora worldwide. For example, the plastic pollution in the Mediterranean Sea has been recognized as

49 the highest of the world's seas, leading to the interaction of plastic litter with marine biota. Ingestion
50 and entanglement are the major interactions documented in the literature (Deudero and Alomar, 2015).
51 Since marine litter is associated with anthropogenic activity, there are spatial variations of litter
52 abundance. For instance, a study conducted in Brazil indicated that beach litter was directly related to
53 the number of beach users. The most urbanized beaches recorded the highest litter compared to the less
54 urbanized beaches (Araújo et al., 2018). Moreover, the type, abundance, and distribution of marine litter
55 are primarily influenced by plastic production, coastal population, oceanographic condition, proximity
56 to urban outflows, and river mouths (Ioakeimidis et al., 2014; Rech et al., 2014; Willis et al., 2017). A
57 study in Nordic seas indicated that high-density litter was found in fjords, marine canyons, and close to
58 the coast. In addition, the study revealed that fishing-related litter was the most dominant (Buhl-
59 Mortensen and Buhl-Mortensen, 2017). In the same vein, research done in four Greek Gulfs (Patras,
60 Corinth, Echinades, and Lakonikos) showed that the dominant litter identified were plastic (56%), metal
61 (17%), and glass (11%). A typological analysis of the litter implied three primary sources: land-based
62 (9%), vessel-based (26%), and fishery-based (5%) (Koutsodendris et al., 2008). Considering all this
63 evidence, marine litter is composed of different materials that vary in space and time. Hence, a
64 comprehensive approach is necessary to address marine litter problems and pave the way for a solution.

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Fig. 1 Map of the Red Sea and surrounding countries and ports.

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The Red Sea is an inlet of the Indian Ocean, semi-enclosed by Egypt, Saudi-Arabia, Sudan, Eritrea,

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Djibouti, Jordan, Israel, and Yemen (Fig 1). It hosts a rich ecosystem, offering a habitat for coral reefs,

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coral fish, mangroves (Abdel-Wahab, 2005), and marine mammals such as dugongs (Gladstone et al.,

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2006) and cetaceans (Costa et al., 2019). The Red Sea's biodiversity is comparable to that of the famous

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Coral Triangle (BCMR, 2020). The present paper critically reviews articles on marine litter in the Red

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Sea, using a search of Scopus and PubMed databases. The available information and the research gaps

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are summarized into different facets of the environmental indicators, namely drivers, pressure, state,

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impact, and response (DPSIR). The research on marine litter in the Red Sea is not extensive and mainly

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focuses on quantitative and qualitative litter assessment. The importance and originality of this review

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are in exploring the causal relationship between the environment and society to communicate the

77 existing problem. Moreover, policy recommendations are provided to address and mitigate the state of
78 marine litter in the Red Sea.

79 **2. Methods**

80 We undertook a literature review using the Scopus and PubMed databases. A search by title, abstract,
81 and keyword was performed using the following search term: ("Red Sea" OR Sudan OR Egypt OR
82 Jordan OR "Saudi Arabia" OR Aqaba OR Eilat OR Eritrea) AND (marine AND (litter OR plastic))
83 (Fig. 2). We further restricted the search to papers published since 2009, yielding 60 articles. These
84 were filtered for relevancy through inspection of the articles, narrowing them down to 24 papers relating
85 directly to Marine Litter in the Red Sea. Additionally, four papers covered plastic pollution in the
86 African continent or Arabian Gulf. These papers did not cover the Red Sea but have some relevance as
87 they add data on plastic consumption and waste management in countries bordering the Red Sea. The
88 literature review was further augmented with a search of grey literature, such as policy documents,
89 reports for the current response landscape, and available citizen science information.

90 Following a methodology utilized in previous studies (Abalansa et al., 2020; Löhr et al., 2017; Miranda
91 et al., 2020), we employed the well-known Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR)
92 framework in the analysis, extracting information from each paper along the categories of the DPSIR
93 causal chain. The advantages of this approach are both structuring the information in a way that
94 promotes effective management of litter, as well as providing an indication of which categories have
95 received more research attention and where knowledge gaps exist.

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Fig. 2 Articles screening and selection for the DPSIR analysis.

98 To avoid anomalies in classification, we used the typology defined by the EEA (Smeets and Weterings,

99 1999); whereby drivers describe the social, demographic, and economic developments in societies and

100 the corresponding changes in lifestyles, including overall levels of consumption and production

101 patterns; pressure in the context of marine litter is mainly measured as changes in emission of litter to

102 the environment; the state is given by a description of the quantity and quality of physical, biological

103 or chemical phenomena in the area under consideration; impact is measured in terms of consequences

104 to social welfare, and response indicators refer to responses by groups (and individuals) in society, as

105 well as government attempts to prevent, compensate, ameliorate or adapt to changes in the state of the

106 environment.

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108 3. DPSIR analysis

109 Most of the publications reviewed (18 of 24) focused on state, with the primary research question an
110 assessment of the abundance of marine litter, including both microplastics (MP) and macro litter (ML),
111 with 9 studies focusing on MP and 9 on ML. Additional 4 publications examined potential sink
112 mechanisms for plastic pollution in the Red Sea, with 3 studies focusing on MP and 1 on ML. One
113 outlier was a study examining coastal zone management of the Jordanian gulf of Aqaba. Although not
114 the primary research goal, many of the publications touched on drivers and pressure. Impact was the
115 least studied area, with one article providing a measure of impact.

116 The geographical distribution of studies is not uniform and is weighted more towards the higher income
117 economies, with 15 studies covering the state of the Red Sea along the coasts of Saudi Arabia, several
118 studies along the coast of Jordan (3 studies) and Egypt (3 studies), one study each to Israel, Eritrea, and
119 Sudan, and none to Yemen and Djibouti. [Fig. 3](#) provides a graphical DPSIR framework of the Red Sea
120 marine litter problem. The following sections dive into details of the drivers, pressure, state, impact,
121 and response as found in the literature search.

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123 **Fig. 3** DPSIR (Drivers, Pressure, State, Impact and Response) framework of the Red Sea marine litter.

124 **3.1 Drivers**

125 The Red Sea's coast is scantily populated, and the area has evaded the coastal population pressure seen
 126 along the shores of other seas and oceans, such as along the Mediterranean. The largest cities are Jeddah
 127 (Saudi Arabia) with a population of over 4 million, Suez (Egypt) with a population of 750,000, Al
 128 Hudaydah (Yemen) with a population of 689,000, Port Sudan (Sudan) with a population of 493,000
 129 (Zeeshan Habib and Thiemann, 2022), and Eritrean sea ports with a population of 70,000 (Massawa
 130 and Assab).

131 In terms of income level, according to the world bank 2022 classification: Eritrea, Sudan, Djibouti and
 132 Yemen are in the low-income level category; Egypt and Jordan are in the lower-middle and upper-
 133 middle income level categories, respectively; Israel and Saudi Arabia are in the high-income category
 134 (WBG, 2021). Population growth and increase in urbanization in the coastal cities of Eilat and Aqaba,
 135 alongside the growth in tourism, shipping, and fishing activities in these cities, are identified as drivers

136 for marine litter along the Jordan Gulf of Aqaba (A. Abu-Hilal and Al-Najjar, 2009a). Industrialization,
137 particularly the growth of Jordan's plastic industry, led to a growth in import of virgin plastic pellets
138 and is also considered a driver for litter in the Gulf of Aqaba. Furthermore, there are poor practices
139 during routine port operations, which for instance, resulted in the spillage of plastic pallets in Aqaba
140 port (A. H. Abu-Hilal and Al-Najjar, 2009).

141 Ruiz-Compean et al. (2017) provide a first evaluation of the sediment contamination in shallow coastal
142 waters of the Red Sea. Even though the focus was on PAH (Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon) and
143 metal pollution, (micro) plastic debris was included in the study. The higher amounts of microplastics
144 were associated with either industrial or densely populated areas.

145 Increase in tourism and recreational activity (including recreational boating and fishing) is mentioned
146 as a primary driver by several authors. Specifically, recreational activity has been identified as a driver
147 through classification of the macro litter composition (A. Abu-Hilal and Al-Najjar, 2009b; Kitto and
148 Sambhu, 2012; Martin et al., 2021). Even in the remote rural area of the Dungenab Bay-Mukkawar
149 Island Marine National Park in Sudan, and the Green Island in Eritrea, classification and timeliness of
150 litter suggests recreational activity is an important driver (Ghebrezgabher et al., 2021; Ibrahim et al.,
151 2020). Fig. 4 shows the dramatic increase in international tourist arrivals from 1995 to 2010. Tourism
152 is not evenly split, in Eritrea, Yemen and Sudan tourism is undeveloped, while it is considerable in
153 Egypt and Saudi Arabia.

154

155 [Fig. 4](#) Tourist arrivals to countries bordering the Red Sea from 1995 to 2010 modified after [\(Gladstone](#)
 156 [et al., 2013\)](#).

157 According to data from the World Travel and Tourism Council ([WTTC, 2022](#)), at its peak, in 2007-
 158 2008, tourism contributed 16.7% of Egypt’s total GDP and generated over 3.6 million jobs. In 2019 the
 159 contribution to GDP dropped to 9%, and the number of jobs was 2.49 million. The same source reports
 160 a GDP contribution of 9.5% for Saudi Arabia in 2019, with 1.454 million jobs. Note that these numbers
 161 are per country rather than for the Red Sea region, yet it is safe to assume the regional trends are similar.
 162 The year 2020-2021 saw a hiatus in travel due to the COVID-19 pandemic; tourism is expected to
 163 bounce back and grow fast. Tourism can be a strategic source of income and hence leverage to motivate
 164 stakeholders toward protecting the coastal and marine ecosystem, which in turn, attracts tourists. On
 165 the other hand, tourism is causing environmental pressure, both due to damage inflicted by tourism-
 166 related coastal development as well as tourist activities.

167 A new related driver is the increase in the use of personal protective equipment, primarily the massive
168 increase of gloves, face masks, and various sorts of wrapping made from single-use plastics, due to the
169 COVID-19 outbreak (Hassan et al., 2022).

170 Another important driver mentioned by multiple sources is maritime traffic (Martin et al., 2019c;
171 Zeeshan Habib and Thiemann, 2022). The Red Sea is a heavily trafficked sea, as approximately 15%
172 of all global maritime trade and 10% of global seaborne oil passes through the Red Sea and the Suez
173 Canal (Kostianaia et al., 2020). The fact that maritime traffic is an important driver for marine litter in
174 the Red Sea was observed from the correlation of litter trapped in mangrove forests to the vicinity of
175 the location to major shipping routes in a short (<15 km) range (Martin et al., 2019b). Furthermore,
176 according to Comolli (2021), the Red Sea seems to be a shipping route for the illegal trade of waste
177 (mainly from Europe to South-East Asia).

178 **3.2 Pressure**

179 While estimates exist for the flow of plastic marine debris to the world's oceans at a country-level
180 resolution (Jambeck et al., 2015), these estimates cannot be used for extracting the estimated flow into
181 the Red Sea as many of the countries surrounding the Red Sea have additional coasts. Significantly,
182 Egypt (which ranks 7th in the percentage of worldwide mismanaged plastic) is densely populated along
183 the Nile River, which carries litter to the Mediterranean rather than the Red Sea.

184 Due to the arid nature of the Red Sea area, there is practically no flow of water from land to sea. Hence
185 riverine mechanisms for transport of litter from land to the marine environment, which are considered
186 a main pathway in other areas, are not significant and are replaced by wind as a major transport
187 mechanism (Martin et al., 2021). Circulation patterns have also been identified as an important factor

188 affecting marine plastic abundance and distribution (Martin et al., 2019a). Evaporation loss in the Red
189 Sea is compensated for by an inflow from the Gulf of Aden. The inflow is pushed north by prevailing
190 winds, with highly saline dense bottom water circulating south. It is estimated that the water in the Red
191 Sea will be replaced in roughly 20 years.

192 The combination of each facet of the driving forces, such as population growth, heavy marine traffic,
193 and tourism, has led to the pressure of increased inflow of litter to the coastal and marine environment.
194 Although quantitative evaluation of marine litter emissions was not uncovered in the literature review,
195 a few studies have analyzed litter composition to obtain an indication of the relative importance of
196 emission sources. For example, studies on the Saudi Arabian shoreline showed that recreational-related
197 litter is more dominant than fishing-related litter (Martin et al., 2021). Similarly, littering from sea-front
198 sectors, including public beaches, ferry terminals, marina, industrial and container terminals, were
199 identified as litter sources (Alrowwad et al., 2020). This finding was supported by Abu-Hilal and Al-
200 Najjar (2009a), who found that most of the litter on the Jordanian coastline of the Gulf of Aqaba results
201 from recreational and shipping activities, with contribution from commercial and recreational fishing.
202 The latter was particularly prominent in one of the locations (Ras Al Yamaneya), which showed an
203 anomalously high percentage (88.33%) of fishing-related debris.

204 Poor waste management practices can exacerbate pressure when coupled with urban and industrial
205 development. For example, poor practices during routine port operations at Aqaba Port have been found
206 to result in spillage of plastic and plastic pellets (A. H. Abu-Hilal and Al-Najjar, 2009; Ruiz-Compean
207 et al., 2017). This activity leads to an increase in floating marine debris in surface water (Martí et al.,
208 2017). Poor waste management is also mentioned in the context of Saudi Arabia, where plastic is the

209 second most common waste with only 10-20% of plastic waste reused or recycled (Dhavamani et al.,
210 2022). Recently, COVID-19-related PPE (personal protective equipment) has also added an extra influx
211 of litter into the Red Sea. A recent study by Hassan et al. (2022) observed that direct littering of PPE is
212 common by beach goers (" visitors tend to leave their plastic litter on the beach instead of using litter
213 bins.").

214 3.3 State

215 3.3.1 Macro litter

216 An assessment of plastic litter using drones along the coast of Saudi Arabia on the Eastern shores of the
217 Red Sea revealed a mean litter density of 0.12 ± 0.02 litter items per meter square (Martin et al., 2021).
218 According to this study, litter was dominated by drink bottles ($39.9 \pm 5.2\%$), followed by anthropogenic
219 wood ($13.5\% \pm 4.3\%$) and bottles for other liquids ($9.1 \pm 1.7\%$). Drinking bottles and bottles for other
220 liquids contributed more than half of the total mass of plastic.

221 A census of marine litter conducted in the western shores of the Red Sea, at the World Heritage Site of
222 Dungonab Bay and Mukkawar Island National Park (DMNP) located in Sudan, found a higher mean
223 density of 0.4 items per meter square (Ibrahim et al., 2020). According to this study, plastics accounted
224 for 57.2% of litter items, followed by processed wood at 12.6%, and fishing gear at 8.5% of items.
225 Marine debris was assessed on the Green Island of Eritrea, an uninhabited nature reserve ed nature
226 reserve located one mile from the Massawa port (Ghebrezgabher et al., 2021). Beach marine debris was
227 collected and classified over a period of five months within five selected transects (5m x 5m) of the
228 coast. Here too, plastic (mostly bottles and foamed plastics) was the most abundant litter, accounting

229 for an overall 82% of macro litter. Applying the Clean Coastal Index (CCI) revealed an overall moderate
230 quality.

231 In another study, submerged debris was removed and collected from six underwater sites within coral
232 reef areas along the Jordanian coast of the Gulf of Aqaba (A. Abu-Hilal and Al-Najjar, 2009b). Mean
233 density of litter was 2.8 items/m². Plastic accounted for 42% of the collected items, fishing gear was the
234 second most abundant (31%). Approximately 61% of the plastics consisted of bags, followed by bottles
235 (24%). Macro Litter was also found in Mangrove forests along the eastern Red Sea coast (Martin et al.,
236 2019b), with drink bottles being the most frequent item, followed by plastic bags and oil containers.
237 The study demonstrated a higher density of larger items compared to beach census, suggesting that
238 mangroves trap marine litter, with the pneumatophores acting as a sieve that retains large plastic objects.

239 **3.3.2 Micro litter**

240 A recent review of MP abundance in the Red Sea by Zeeshan Habib and Thiemann (2022) covered
241 twenty publications, which almost exclusively focused on the eastern shoreline of the Red Sea. A main
242 result of the review was that abundance of MP in the Red Sea is low compared to other marine areas.
243 For example, Martí et al. (2017) used the trawling method to cover 1,500 km of the Saudi Arabian
244 coastline of the Red Sea and reported an MP abundance of 3,546 items/km² (1.08 g km⁻²), 40 times
245 lower than findings using comparable sampling methods in the Mediterranean Sea. Several subsequent
246 works attempt to explain the low abundance of surface MP through sink mechanisms attributed to
247 mangroves, corals, and clams (Arossa et al., 2019; Martin et al., 2021, 2019c).

248 However, other findings suggest a higher abundance of MP, with large variability in findings depending
249 on the method, location, and season. Martin et al. (2019a) deployed a neuston net to collect surface MP

250 at a pelagic station in the central Red Sea. They found a high variation of MP with season, with a median
251 abundance of 19,777 items/km² (8.05 g km⁻²), an order of magnitude higher than the median values
252 estimated for the entire basin in the study by Marti et al, which they attributed to a plastic hotspot at
253 this location. [Baalkhuyur et al. \(2018\)](#) searched for MP in the gastrointestinal tract of fish, sampling
254 178 fish (26 species) collected from four different habitats along the Saudi Arabian coast. Microplastic
255 fragments were found in 14.6% of the sampled fish. In contrast, MP particles were found in 44% of 140
256 fish (6 species) sampled by [Al-Lihaibi et al. \(2019\)](#) near Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. [Sayed et al. \(2021\)](#)
257 recorded the abundance of Microplastic (MP) along the shores of Egypt, collecting data from 4 sites on
258 the western shore of the Red Sea and 4 sites on the southern Mediterranean shore, finding comparable
259 levels of MP in both waters, sediment, and fish in the Mediterranean and the Red Sea sites. According
260 to their study, MP abundance in the water varied between 50 to 66 particles/100 mL in the Red Sea and
261 between 47 to 69 particles/100 mL in the Mediterranean, while MP concentration in fish were in the
262 range of 2-5 particles per fish in the Red Sea, which was only slightly lower than for the Mediterranean
263 (2 to 8).

264 The studies differ in the collection method, yet this alone would not explain the large variance in data
265 and the qualitative gap in the comparison between the Mediterranean concentrations to those in the Red
266 Sea. More research is needed into the abundance of MP in the Red Sea to account for variations in
267 season and location. In particular, care should be taken when concluding that the Red Sea is less polluted
268 than other marine areas based on data coming from surface water sampling of the Eastern coast alone.

269 **3.4 Impact**

270 [Abalansa et al. \(2020\)](#) identify potential impact to human welfare through loss of life (e.g., due to
271 entanglement), health risks (e.g., by contamination of seafood), loss of income (e.g., through reduced
272 visitation due to beach litter or disruption of fishing operations), and loss of wellbeing (e.g., through
273 degradation of use and non-use values). Of the publications included in this literature survey, only one
274 attempted to quantify marine litter impact in this region. This work found a positive correlation between
275 plastic debris and phthalic acid esters abundance in Sharm Obhur and the Red Sea in the vicinity of
276 Jeddah. A risk quotient method was applied to assess the ecological risk associated with phthalic acid
277 esters, revealing a low to moderate risk, with average health index values ranging from 0.43 to 0.55
278 ([Dhavamani et al., 2022](#)).

279 In addition, several studies briefly touch on the topic, mainly in the context of ingestion of marine litter
280 by fish and shellfish, [Baalkhuyur et al. \(2018\)](#) report on MP ingested by both commercial and non-
281 commercial fish, noting the potential presence of hazardous chemical compounds, such as phthalates
282 and bisphenol A, with possible impacts on fish health transferred along the food web. Similarly, the
283 environmental impact of ingestion of plastic pellets by seabirds and fish is mentioned by [Abu-Hilal and](#)
284 [Al-Najjar \(\(2009\)](#). [Arossa et al. \(2019\)](#) mention the potential impact of MP ingestion by clams. While
285 the economic impacts of marine litter in the Red Sea have not been explored, scenery evaluation of
286 Rabigh coastline implied the degradation of scene quality due to litter ([Alharbi and Rangel-Buitrago,](#)
287 [2022](#)).

288 **3.5 Responses**

289 The response to the problem of marine litter is polycentric, with multiple actors and instruments
290 involved, including international, regional, and national policies, NGO campaigns, and scientific

291 research. Several policies have been implemented in the last years ([Table 1](#)).

292 **Table 1** The regulatory framework composing the response to marine litter in the Red Sea.

	National	Regional	International
Egypt	National Waste Management Law № 202 of 2020, ban on single-use plastic items (Hurghada, HEPCA)	PERSGA	
Eritrea	Minimum threshold for produced plastic		
Israel	Law for the Reduction of the use of Disposable Carrying Bags-2016, partial ban on manufacture, free retail distribution, and importation of plastic bags, EPR for packaging, container deposit legislation and waste management legislation		
Jordan	Green Growth National Action Plan 2021-2025, National Strategy and Action Plan for Municipal Solid Waste 2015-2034, minimum threshold for plastic production	PERSGA	UNCLOS, MARPOL (Annex V), Plastic Waste Amendment (Basel Convention)
Saudi Arabia	Royal Decree №. M/3 of 2021 (Waste Management System), min. threshold of produced plastic (If less, oxo-degradable, then bio-degradable)	PERSGA	
Sudan	Environmental Health Act № 1 of 2009, Environmental Protection and Promotion Law in Khartoum State of 2008	PERSGA	
Yemen	Law № 16 of 2004 on the Protection of the Marine Environment from Pollution; partial ban on manufacture, free retail distribution, and importation of plastic bags.	PERSGA	

293 [Zeeshan Habib and Thiemann \(2022\)](#), in their review of MP in the Red Sea, mention the Regional
 294 Organization for the Conservation of the Environment of the Red Sea and Gulf of Aden (PERSGA
 295 2018), and specifically one of its programs addressing national capacity building for marine litter
 296 management, focusing on better waste-management, and awareness creation. The ban on single-use
 297 plastic issued by HEPCA is outlined too.

298 [Ibrahim et al. \(2020\)](#), in their study of beach litter in DMNP, conclude that beach litter is manageable,
 299 with the application of preventive measures and public awareness activities while leveraging the
 300 tendency for solid waste reuse typical of low-income rural communities. Nevertheless, beach litter
 301 monitoring was proposed to gain more scientific and accurate data. In 2016, the “MPA Outreach and
 302 Education Plan”, issued by [PERSGA \(2016\)](#), highlighted environmental and communication problems

303 in DMNP, suggesting a raise in public awareness campaigns, MPA social marketing campaigns, and
304 capacity building (particularly for members of the DMNP authorities).

305 Plastic litter was found on Jordan's coasts and raised concerns. The need for standardized monitoring
306 programs and investment in education and awareness campaigns was a common theme in several
307 studies conducted (A. H. Abu-Hilal and Al-Najjar, 2009; Al-Najjar and Al-Shiyab, 2011). For example,
308 studies highlighted the importance and accuracy of data gathered during marine clean-up campaigns
309 (Al-Najjar and Al-Shiyab, 2011), as well as the need for an analysis of sediments for microplastics and
310 other pollutants to establish baseline indices that will drive national guidelines (Ruiz-Compean et al.,
311 2017). The potential benefit of educational activity was particularly showcased by Abu-Hilal and Al-
312 Najjar (2009), where education and guidance to prevent inappropriate handling of pellets at the port of
313 Aqaba could potentially prevent spillage of pellets. On the contrary, in the study of Hemidat et al.
314 (2022), the data of waste collected in Jordan showed that waste consisted more of organic material, but
315 an increasing trend towards plastic waste can be observed.

316 Additionally, the establishment of infrastructures in order to ensure safe informal waste collection and
317 recycling in less-developed countries was mentioned by Hassan et al. (2022), who emphasized the
318 importance of further research and improved products and policies to enhance better behavior regarding
319 consumption and disposal of PPE products. Stöfen-O'Brien et al. (2022) mentioned the national
320 legislation in Saudi Arabia regulating the thickness of plastic bags.

321 **3.5.1 International instruments**

322 Legally binding international instruments include the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
323 (UNCLOS), the Basel Convention, and The International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution

324 from Ships (MARPOL). UNCLOS is the main legal framework for marine and maritime activities,
325 defining the rights and responsibilities of nations with respect to their use of the world's oceans. It is the
326 first internationally binding agreement to address land-based marine pollution sources, mandating
327 States to adopt laws and regulations to prevent, reduce and control pollution of the marine environment
328 from land-based sources (Article 207), and to enforce these laws (Article 213) (Chen, 2015).

329 The Plastic Waste Amendment to the Basel convention, adopted in 2019 and effective as of 1st January
330 2021, seeks to bring tighter governance on the transboundary movement of plastic waste, whereby
331 plastic waste that is hazardous or difficult to recycle will require advanced consent from the importing
332 country in form of a Prior Informed Consent (PIC) securing that the waste will be managed in an
333 environmentally sound manner in the importing country (Syberg et al., 2021). Non-hazardous, clean,
334 and sorted plastic waste destined for recycling in an environmentally sound manner, can be traded
335 without applying the PIC procedure.

336 Annex V of MARPOL focuses on preventing pollution from waste by ships and introduces a complete
337 ban on the disposal in the sea of all forms of plastics. Moreover, the Red Sea was designated a 'special
338 area' status under MARPOL Annex V (providing it a higher level of protection). However,
339 implementation of MARPOL Annex V is lagging, and the special area status for the Red Sea has not
340 entered into force due to lack of sufficient port reception facilities in bordering countries (IMO, 2021).

341 Key relevant international soft-law instruments include the Regional Seas Programme
342 (introduced in 1974), the Global Programme of Action (GPA) for the Protection of the Marine
343 Environment from Land-based Activities (adopted in 1995), the Honolulu Strategy (created in
344 2011) as well as the 2030 agenda for sustainable development and sustainable development

345 goals, which were adopted in 2015 (Kerber, 2017).

346 In 2017, UNEP implemented the global campaign *Clean Seas*, to reduce single-use plastic through a
347 change in regulation or legislation. Israel, Jordan, Yemen, and Sudan are signatories. Furthermore,
348 UNEP plans to issue a Global Plastic Treaty, an international legally binding instrument, addressing
349 and improving the full lifecycle of plastic (production, design and disposal) (UNEP, 2022).

350 **3.5.2 Regional instruments**

351 The Regional Organization for Conservation of the Environment of the Red Sea and the Gulf of Aden,
352 (formerly called “The Programme for the Environment of the Red Sea and Gulf of Aden”) PERSGA,
353 is an intergovernmental organization with seven member states: Djibouti, Egypt, Jordan, the Kingdom
354 of Saudi Arabia, Somalia, Sudan, and Yemen. The organization is hosted by the Kingdom of Saudi
355 Arabia. With the support of the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP), PERSGA was
356 underpinned by the signing of the Jeddah Convention, which “expresses in clear terms the commitment
357 and the political will of the governments of the region to tackle the marine and coastal environments of
358 the Red Sea and the Gulf of Aden through joint and coordinated efforts” (PERSGA, 2018). PERSGA
359 has also committed to the protocol concerning the conservation of biological diversity and the
360 establishment of the network of protected areas in the Red Sea and Gulf of Aden (PERSGA, 2005a)
361 and the protocol concerning the protection of the marine environment from land-based activities in the
362 Red Sea and Gulf of Aden (PERSGA, 2005b). Their most recent Regional Action Plan (hereby referred
363 to as RAP) (PERSGA, 2018) provides a roadmap toward sustainable management of marine litter, with
364 a list of 60 actions linked to one of seven strategies designed to address the threat of marine litter
365 comprehensively. Component 5 consists of six actions for marine litter clean-ups and collections,
366 including an overview of national strategies and collaborations with stakeholders. Component 6
367 describes the importance of long-term monitoring and studies and mentions some actions (e.g., clean-
368 ups) in addition to establishing standardizing protocols to evaluate marine litter. Guidelines for
369 monitoring coastal marine litter were published in 2014 (PERSGA, 2014), together with advice on how

370 to raise public awareness. In 2020, the report “state of the marine environment”, SOMERSGA II, was
371 released, assessing the impact of human activities on the Red Sea and the Gulf of Aden. The issue of
372 marine debris was briefly mentioned but concluded that there is no solid, comprehensive baseline
373 information about marine litter, but it was suggested to carry out regular beach clean-ups ([PERSGA,](#)
374 [2020](#)).

375 **3.5.3 National policies**

376 **Egypt**

377 The study by [Ibrahim and Mohamed \(2016\)](#), mentions that solid waste management in Egypt is still
378 given a low priority, as funds are limited and public services insufficient. The study confirmed that it is
379 still common practice to dispose domestic and industrial waste illegally. Furthermore, the accumulation
380 of untreated garbage has led to environmental and health threats, especially in Cairo. However, it is
381 important to mention that only 5% of Egypt’s produced municipal solid waste comes from the Sinai
382 and the Red Sea region.

383 According to the UNEP Global Review of National Laws and Regulations, there is no ban on the
384 manufacture, free distribution, and importation of plastic bags in Egypt; the disposal is only regulated
385 at national level ([UNEP, 2018](#)). According to the [FAOLEX Database \(2020\)](#), an outline of Egypt’s
386 National Waste Management Law No 202. of 2020 forbids dumping “waste into the regional sea,
387 continental shelf, exclusive economic zone or high seas of Egypt”. The law includes a subsection on
388 single-use plastic bags, providing for tighter control on their manufacture, trade, storage, distribution,
389 and disposal, and accommodating economic measures to encourage environmentally friendly
390 alternatives for single-use plastic bags. Additionally, the waste management authority and the Ministry

391 of Commerce and Industry introduced a “green label” system, which should ensure the sustainable
392 production of goods in order to limit the generation of non-recyclable waste.

393 **Eritrea**

394 Since January 2002, a law in Eritrea prohibits the importation, production, distribution, or the sale of
395 thin plastic bags. Plastic bags are replaced by cotton and nylon bags, and everyone who does not follow
396 this law might receive a high fine. The minimum threshold for plastic bag thickness is 100 micrometers
397 (UNEP, 2018). Regulation to prohibit the production, Sale, or Distribution of Plastic Bags in Eritrea
398 (L.N. No. 63 of 2002), new Article 2: “It shall be prohibited to produce, import, sell or distribute any
399 plastic bags of high density or low-density polyethylene product not exceeding 0,1 millimeter in
400 thickness” (MOIE, 2017).

401 **Israel**

402 According to Daskal et al. (2018), municipal solid waste is still most commonly disposed at landfill
403 sites. Waste is collected by public and private sectors and consists mainly of plastics (41.1%), paper
404 (15.8%), cardboard (12.2), and organic waste (11.6%) if measured by volume, or organic material
405 (34%), plastics (18%), paper (16%), and cardboard (8%) if measured by weight. Due to the
406 environmental impacts of the landfills, since 2007, there is a landfill levy, and since 2010 there has been
407 a financial support program for the separation of waste (into two streams: biodegradable and remainder).
408 However, the infrastructure to handle two separate waste streams is insufficient.

409 According to the FAOLEX Database (2004), there are several laws responsible for waste management
410 and protection of the sea: Waste Collection and Clearing for Recycling Purposes Law (1993), Undersea

411 Water Lands Law (1953), Prevention of Sea Pollution. From Land-Based Sources Law (1988) and the
412 Prevention of Sea Pollution (Dumping of Waste) Law, (1983). Responsible entities are the Ministry of
413 the Environment and the Ministry of the Interior.

414 There is a partial ban on the manufacture, free retail distribution, and importation of plastic bags in
415 Israel, with a levy imposed by the law to reduce the use of disposable carrying bags. Israel law adopted
416 the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) approach, whereby producers and importers of goods have
417 responsibility for the “after-life” of product packaging, including collection and recycling of packaging.
418 There are mandatory annual targets for collecting empty beverage containers: manufacturers must
419 collect at least 73% of beverage containers up to 1.5 L and 55% above 1.5 L and recycle at least 90%
420 of them, as regulated by the Deposit on Beverage Containers Law. No regulations for microbeads were
421 found ([Lavee, 2010](#); [UNEP, 2018](#)).

422 Eilat was the first city in Israel to ban the use of single-use plastic on its beaches. The bylaw was
423 approved in December 2020 ([MEP, 2020](#)), helping to prevent plastic litter from beach visitation.
424 Additional policies in place to fight plastic pollution in Israel include a ‘clean beach’ program led by
425 the ministry of environment, which includes regular beach monitoring, and a container deposit scheme
426 for plastic bottles. However, plastic litter remains a concern in all of Israel’s coasts (the Mediterranean
427 and the Red Sea) ([Vered et al., 2019](#)).

428 **Jordan**

429 According to the country report on solid waste management by [GIZ \(2014\)](#), there is no solid waste
430 policy in Jordan; however, the main agency responsible for the management of solid waste is the
431 Ministry of Environment and the Ministry of Municipal Affairs. In the study of [Aldayyat et al. \(2019\)](#),

432 it was mentioned that in the absence of proper waste management systems, Jordan’s garbage ends up
433 in engineered landfills (50%), controlled dumps (35%), open dumped (5%) or recycled (6-10%). Waste
434 is usually collected by formal and informal “waste-pickers”. According to UNEP 2018 (UNEP, 2019)
435 report, Aqaba city is implementing circular procedure to reduce solid waste generation.

436 Even though recycling and waste separation programs are still not developed on a formal level, it
437 appears that the Jordan government has reacted to this issue: The “Green Growth National Action Plan
438 2021-2025” and the “National Strategy and Action Plan for Municipal Solid Waste Management 2015-
439 2034” are currently active. Their goals are, i.e., to increase the diversion of waste away from landfills
440 (through the reduce, recycle, and reuse approach), to build a sustainable business model which offsets
441 the cost of waste management for urban areas, to encourage private sector investment and job creation
442 in the circular economy, to mainstream critical waste streams into sector priorities (including
443 construction and demolition waste, e-waste and hazardous waste) or reducing GHG, could be reached
444 (MoEnv, 2020). According to UNEP (2018), there is a ban on plastic bags thinner than 200 micrometers.

445 **Saudi Arabia**

446 The management of solid waste is ruled by the Local Affair and Ministry of Municipalities and local
447 municipalities. They are responsible for collecting, transporting, and disposing of waste to either
448 incineration sites, landfills, or dump sites, of which Makkah landfill and Buraiman (Jeddah) are the
449 biggest. The majority of waste consists of organic material (65%), followed by plastics (5.2%), which
450 has emphasized constructing compost facilities to convert food waste into reusable agricultural
451 products. However, studies showed that most of the produced compost did not comply with
452 international standards (Adebayo Bello and bin Ismail, 2016).

453 According to the outline of the Royal Decree No. M/3 of 2021 issuing the Waste Management System,
454 the national responsible entity is the National Waste Management Center (NWMC). Article 11 states
455 that resources and materials must be reused, reduced, and recycled properly, in Article 12, the waste
456 management for marine vehicles and ports is outlined, and article 14 highlights the EPR for producers
457 and importers ([FAOLEX Database, 2021](#)).

458 The Global Review of [UNEP \(2018\)](#), states that there is a regulation regarding the requirement of the
459 thickness of plastic produced and imported to Saudi Arabia, enforced by the Saudi-Arabian Standard
460 Organization (SASO). Currently, the minimum thickness is 250 microns. Disposable plastic products
461 made of polypropylene and polyethylene with a film thickness of less than or equal to 250 microns
462 (rally used for packaging) must be made of the oxo-biodegradable type and include a certain logo. Any
463 other plastic products intended for single use only are prohibited (material and product ban).

464 A national action plan for managing marine litter is in progress, conducted by PERSGA, and a final
465 draft is soon to be approved. It includes sections about raising public awareness, adequacy of port
466 reception facilities, engagement plans of stakeholders and private companies, management of single-
467 use plastic bags, and support to local marine research institutes. Furthermore, there is a new draft of
468 “Waste Management Law”, including waste minimization, segregation, and recycling improvements.
469 It should include the implementation of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), monitoring and
470 penalties for violations regarding illegal dumping and burning of waste. A study by the National Center
471 for Waste Management (NCWM) has been launched, which should introduce a ban on single-use plastic
472 and user fees ([Kato et al., 2021](#)).

473 **Sudan**

474 According to a study by [Abdellah and Balla \(2013\)](#), there are landfills, incineration facilities to convert
475 waste into energy, and open waste-burning places in Sudan. Domestic waste is collected and transferred
476 by trucks, but it remains unclear if Sudan's waste management is generally sufficient.

477 Currently, there is the Environment Health Act No. 1 of 2009 and the Environmental Protection and
478 Promotion Law in Khartoum State of 2008, which consists of acts dealing with the protection of the
479 environment as well as the implementation of solid waste management. It also outlined how to combat
480 pollution and stop the negative effects deriving from economic, agricultural, and industrial activities.
481 There is also a section about the importance of increasing environmental awareness in the population
482 and defining the methods of waste management, their treatment, and their reuse ([FAOLEX Database,](#)
483 [2009, 2008](#)).

484 **Yemen**

485 In Yemen, solid waste is transferred to poorly managed landfills. There have been cleaning attempts in
486 some Yemeni towns where a lot of plastic items were collected and recycled by low-income families,
487 but thin plastic bags were not included in the collection as they were considered useless. Up to now,
488 (unregulated) open crude dumping is the most common waste management strategy in Yemen, but this
489 method is considered extremely harmful to both the environment and humans. It is important to mention
490 that Yemen has been, and still is, in a situation of conflict; however, recently, there are attempts of
491 waste recycling ([Al-Dailami et al., 2022](#)).

492 Despite the difficult past and current situation in Yemen, there is Law No. 16 of 2004 on the Protection
493 of the Marine Environment from Pollution. For instance, it is stated that it is forbidden for any person,
494 vessel, aircraft, or transfer oil vehicle to discharge any contaminated material in a so-called “pollution-

495 free” zone. Furthermore, monitoring procedures are outlined for every ship to follow as well as legal
496 actions if these procedures are not followed. According to [UNEP \(2018\)](#), there is a ban on
497 manufacturing plastic bags thinner than 70 microns. Additionally, there is a ban on manufacturing and
498 using non-biodegradable plastic bags.

499 **3.5.4 Other Inter-regional and International Organizations, NGOs, and citizen science**

500 The Heinrich Böll Foundation focuses on international projects regarding human rights and the
501 environment. There are several projects around plastic waste, one of them is working on the
502 consequences of plastics on the Red Sea. According to their website, around 57% of waste found in the
503 Red Sea is plastic ([Al-Tawaha and Geiger, 2019](#)).

504 The Royal Marine Conservation Society of Jordan, JREDS is a partner of the Heinrich Böll Foundation,
505 operating mostly on beaches of the Gulf of Aqaba. Their projects include beach clean-ups and raising
506 awareness. RSEC, a German-based NGO, promotes research, education, and awareness in the Red Sea.
507 Bracenet is a company selling mainly bracelets made from recovered ghost nets. For every product
508 bought, a donation is made to HealthyOceans. According to their website, ghost nests of the Red Sea
509 were also recovered.

510 The Khaled bin Sultan Living Oceans Foundation aims to protect, preserve, and restore the oceans (with
511 a focus on coral reefs) worldwide through research, education, and outreach. The Red Sea Development
512 Company (TRSDC) is building a luxury seafront tourism destination, which should also include a
513 marine debris beach clean-up program and a recycling or upcycling sector of employment. More
514 megacities are planned, i.e., the project AMAALA.

515 Zalul was founded to protect the Red Sea from aquaculture (fish farming) in the Gulf of Aqaba near
516 Eilat, leading a successful campaign that led to their removal. It has since developed to become the
517 leading environmental NGO in Israel dedicated to the protection of the seas and rivers of Israel ([Teff-
518 Seker et al., 2018](#)).

519 The Hurghada Environmental Protection and Conservation Association (HEPCA) is an Egyptian NGO
520 focusing on marine conservation. Since June 1st, 2019, the sale of plastic bags is forbidden in the Red
521 Sea province of Hurghada, excluding the use of heavy-duty garbage bags. HEPCA organizes beach
522 clean-ups in collaboration with dive centers and the Middle East Project Aware of PADI ([PADI, 2022](#)).

523 Within the campaign “Dive Against Debris / Marine Awareness, of PADI, divers collected marine litter
524 and uploaded their data to a globally accessible database ([PADI AWARE, 2022](#)). There are also
525 Thalassians and Banlastic Egypt participating in clean-ups. The Egyptian Startup “Conictus” was
526 founded by Amir Gerges and uses Artificial Intelligence to collect data about oceans.

527 Regarding scientific research, the King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST)
528 offers several master’s and Ph.D. programs and internships, including research about plastic pollution
529 ([KAUST, 2020](#)).

530 **4. Discussion**

531 Applying the DPSIR framework to marine litter in the Red Sea offers a perspective to highlight the
532 unique characteristic of the area’s marine litter problem. While there is lack of research directed at
533 measuring emissions of litter to the Red Sea, the existing studies highlight the role of shipping and
534 recreational activity as important sources of litter. We note that the Red Sea coast is not as densely

535 populated as the coast surrounding other seas and oceans, resulting in a reduced significance of
536 urbanization and industrialization as drivers, while the heavy shipping traffic, alongside the growing
537 tourism industry, are significant drivers generating emissions of litter directly to the Red Sea's coasts
538 and waters.

539 The existing research focuses mainly on the abundance of macro and micro litter. However, the data is
540 both incomplete and inconsistent. Assessments of macro litter along the Red Sea beaches report litter
541 densities between 0.12 to 0.4 items per square meter, dominated by plastic, particularly plastic bottles.
542 Surveys of submerged or entangled litter revealed higher densities of up to 6 items per square meter,
543 once more dominated by plastic (mostly bags and bottles), as well as fishing gear (A. Abu-Hilal and
544 Al-Najjar, 2009a; Ibrahim et al., 2020; Martin et al., 2021). These studies all use the standing-stock
545 survey approach, at a monthly or quarterly interval, where the amount of litter found reflects the long-
546 term balance between inputs and removal (Ryan et al., 2009), with the exception of one study which
547 also measured flux (Ibrahim et al., 2020). More questions are raised by the gap between the low level
548 of microplastics reported in the surface water along the eastern coast of the Red Sea by one study (Martí
549 et al., 2017), and the high abundance of MP found in the water column along the Western coast of Egypt
550 by another (Sayed et al., 2021). These inconsistencies highlight the need for standardization and
551 calibration of microplastic monitoring protocol in the Red Sea.

552 The present work also provides a detailed survey of the responses to marine litter in the Red Sea. A
553 notable conclusion is that the response has accelerated over the last decade with the Regional Action
554 Plan developed in 2018 (PERSGA, 2018). Legislation addressing waste management was established
555 in 2020 in Egypt and 2021 in Saudi Arabia, and a national action plan for marine litter is in progress in

556 Saudi Arabia and it is still evolving. NGO activities are focusing on clean-ups, education and outreach,
557 and research.

558 Finally, it is interesting to cross-correlate the main findings from the scientific literature with the
559 response, in order to identify policy gaps and instruments that could be of high impact. In this regard,
560 the literature review revealed recreation and shipping as primary drivers, while macro litter consistently
561 includes a high portion of plastic bottles and fishing gear. Hence, it is suggested that addressing these
562 drivers and litter items could have a significant impact on the Red Sea plastic problem.

563 For plastic bottles, container deposit legislation is an effective tool capable of reducing the amount of
564 beverage container litter on the coasts by as much as 40% (Schuyler et al., 2018). For an arid area with
565 high volumes of tourist visitation, the availability of high-quality drinking water from taps or water
566 dispensers could also be an effective measure. The RAP has one relevant action item: “Encourage
567 private companies to take initiatives, such as a voluntary phase-out of single-use bags, water bottles and
568 straws and other plastic items”. This is in contrast to, for example, the Regional Plan on Marine Litter
569 Management in the Mediterranean (UNEP(DEPI)/MED, 2013), which specifies a stronger clause
570 calling contracting parties to “Explore and implement to the extent possible prevention measures related
571 to establishment of [mandatory] Deposits, Return and Restoration System for beverage packaging
572 prioritizing, when possible, their recycling”.

573 For fishing gear, the RAP includes one relevant item under the education of “Fishermen on impacts of
574 abandoned fishing gear and other litter on marine resources and habitats”. Fishing gear is also addressed
575 partially by clean-up activities of NGOs. This again can be contrasted with more extensive action

576 prescribed by the Mediterranean regional plan, which includes fishing for litter schemes and gear
577 marking among the prescribed measures.

578 For shipping-related waste, the primary response is through MARPOL annex V, where one of the key
579 enablers is the establishment of adequate port reception facilities to allow the disposal of ship waste.
580 This is recognized by the RAP, which states that most PERSGA member countries are also signatories
581 to the MARPOL convention but that establishing adequate port reception facilities, implementation,
582 and enforcement is weak. The remedy suggested by the RAP is facilitating a workshop to assist member
583 countries to understand their obligations to MARPOL (PERSGA, 2018). Additional measures
584 prescribed by the Mediterranean regional plan and regional plans of the Baltic Seas concern the
585 harmonization of a no-special-fee system in ports.

586 It is suggested that strengthening the instruments either at the regional or national level along these
587 three vectors could help address marine litter in the Red Sea by contending with the main drivers.

588 **5. Conclusion**

589 The present review has integrated the currently available research on marine litter in the Red Sea. Peer-
590 reviewed literature focused on the state and showed that marine litter is abundant but distributed
591 unevenly. Due to inconsistent data, quantifying marine litter was difficult, as research mainly came
592 from higher-income countries and varied temporally and spatially. Response has intensified in the last
593 decade and appears to be still evolving, with instruments at both regional and national levels (e.g.,
594 regional action plan and local bans on single-use plastic items). Suggestions for further actions were
595 obtained through a comparison of the response in the RAP with the drivers and state extracted from the
596 scientific literature. Specifically, three components were identified for strengthening regional and/or

597 national responses, which are: promoting container deposit legislation for increasing the collection rate
598 of plastic containers; initiating fishing for litter schemes to address fishing gear litter; and implementing
599 adequate port reception facilities in accordance with MARPOL to reduce shipping related waste.

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